

The Prime Solar System

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Abstract

A mapping of prime numbers onto a solar system is presented. The Prime Solar System (PSS) can be seen as a physical system that is factorising positive integers. Reversely, the factorisation of integers can be seen as a way to compute the location of the PSS planets. Periodicities of the PSS are translated into periodicities of the factorisation of positive integers. This allow:

- the forecast of the next prime number after the integer N from the knowledge of the configuration of the PSS at time N ,
- the forecast of voids, that is, the location of regions without prime numbers. Voids of length $p_l - 1$ starting at $p_l\# + 1$ and ending at $p_l\# + p_l$ are guaranteed to exist for $l = 1, 2, \dots$,
- the forecast of some factors of large integers from the knowledge of the factors of smaller integers. If $n = q \bmod p_J\#$ is true with $q > p_J\#$ then n and q share the same first J primes as factors and as not-factors.

1 Introduction

As described by classical physics, a solar system is a deterministic periodic system for which the future positions of its planets can be known in advance from the knowledge of their present locations, velocities and accelerations. If a mapping between such a classical system and the prime number set could be established, then one would be facing the exciting perspective of being able to forecast future prime numbers from the knowledge of past prime numbers in analogy with the well known achievements of forecasting the future positions of the planets of a solar system using the physical laws of Nature. As it will be shown later, such kind of forecast of new prime numbers is in fact possible, but in practice, only at a price that is not competitive against the present techniques for testing primality. Nevertheless, the intrinsic periodic nature of planetary orbits can be translate into periodicities of the factorisation of positive integers. Periodicities in the factorisation of integers is a recurrent theme in number theory. However, very few periodicities, if one, have been reported. The scientific literature usually reports the existence of deviations from expected statistical behaviour, which mainly offers a hint on possible regular behaviour, instead of specific values for periods. The report of periodicities based on the isomorphism of periodicities between the Prime Solar System (PSS) and the factorisation of primes is the major contribution of this work.

2 The Prime Solar System

Definition of PSS

The solar system considered in this work is one where the planets and the sun are all in the same plan with each planet orbiting the sun at the same linear velocity as the other planets. The orbits are perfectly circular, and centred at the immobile sun. In addition to the above, the planets and the sun are assumed to behave as geometrical points even if in the following pictures they are represented with some geometrical extended. Time is quantized and only takes the values $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$. The unit of length is Um and the unit of time is Us , where the prefix U represents an arbitrary fraction of an order of magnitude. Units will be easily guessed from the context and will not be systematically stated. For instance, in a sentence as “at time $n = 23$ ” it is assumed that Us is the units used for measuring time. Finally, the period of rotation of the planets and their distances to the sun are directly

proportional to the prime numbers, that is, there is a simple linear bijective mapping between the prime numbers and the rotation periods and distances of the planets to the sun.

Figure 1 shows a PSS with six planets.

Velocities, Distances and Periods

The amplitude of the linear velocity, v , of a prime planet, P_i , can be computed as the ratio between the distance, s_i , traveled by the i^{th} prime planet along its curved path orbit, O_i , and the time, t_i , spent by the planet traveling that distance. This definition is directly derived from the definition of velocity of a body used in Physics. In the case of PSS that velocity is assumed to be independent of the instant, the same for all planets and the same at any point of their trajectories. This can be translated by the the following equation:

$$v = \frac{s_i(t)}{t_i} \quad (1)$$

Another useful quantity for the description of objects rotating about a fixed origin is the angular velocity, w , defined as the quotient between the angle in radians, θ , that an object sweeps through and the time it took to do it, t , that is:

$$w = \frac{\theta}{t} \quad (2)$$

Since the length s of the arc cut off by a central angle in a circle of radius d is given by $s = d\theta$, we can conclude that v and w are related by:

$$v = w_i d_i. \quad (3)$$

Since both v and d_i are constants for each planet Equation 3 tell us that w_i is constant for each planet. In this circumstances w_i can be computed using any finite for duration of time and angle. Fortunately, we know a finite angle and duration for each planet, the duration p_i that the P_i planet takes to go about the sun ($\theta = 2\pi$). Therefore, we can write from Equation 2,

$$w_i = \frac{2\pi}{p_i} \quad (4)$$

Putting this expression back into Equation 3 and assuming that the value of v is 2π , we can further say that:

$$2\pi = \frac{2\pi}{p_i} d_i \quad (5)$$

$$p_i = d_i \quad (6)$$

that is, the period of rotation of each Prime Planet, p_i , is numerically identical to its distance to the Sun, d_i . This equality allow us to refer to the orbit of a planet without explicitly state if we are talking about its period or distance to the Sun. For instance, we can just say “the planet in orbit 13” meaning the planet at a distance of 13Um from the Sun with a period of rotation of 13Ut. Note that this is the sixth planet, P_6 and not the 13th planet. Note also that the choice of the value 2π for the amplitude of the linear velocity is allowed since by definition of PSS the linear velocity has to be time and location independent but its actual value can be arbitrarily chosen.

The Fractional Location function, $L(i, n)$.

The constant value of v in Equation 3 shows that planets far from the sun (longer orbits) will sweep a smaller angle per unit time (smaller angular velocity) relatively to the planets near to the sun (see Figure 2). This is equivalent to say that planets near the sun complete their orbits much faster than planets farther from the sun. For instance, after 1Us, the planet at 2Um from the sun is at half of its trajectory whereas the planet at 3Um from the sun is at a third of its trajectory and the planet at distance d_i is at the fraction $1/d_i$ (or $1/p_i$ since $d_i \equiv p_i$) of its trajectory. In mathematical notation this can be translated by:

$$L(i, n) = \frac{n \bmod p_i}{p_i} \quad (7)$$

where n is the integer time, $L(i, n)$ is the Fractional Location function and “ $n \bmod p_i$ ” denotes the remainder of the division of n by p_i . For instance, at time $n = 47$ the planet on orbit 13 (the 6th planet) is at $L(6, 47) = \frac{47 \bmod 13}{13}$, that is at 8/13 of its orbit. At time $n = 52$ it will be at $0/13 = 0$ of its orbit, that is, at its initial position since $52 \bmod 13$ is 0: the planet has just completed 4 rotations about the sun.

Figure 1: Prime solar system at time 0Us. At the start all planets are aligned. All planets have the same linear velocity which is tangent to their orbits. The 6th planet is on orbit 13th which is 13Um from the sun. All orbits that are not prime numbers have no planet. See Table 1 for more details.

Figure 2: Location of the 6 first prime planets when $t = 1 \text{ Us}$. More information is given in Table (2).

Forecasting the Locations of the Prime Planets in Function of Time

The Fractional Location function, $L(i, n)$, contains all the information needed to describe the trajectory of each known prime planet P_i for all time $n = 1, 2, \dots$. This means that, once guaranteed that the solar system is PSS, we can forget about angular velocities, linear velocities, periods and distances and focus only on the Fractional Location function in order to forecast the future positions of the known prime planets. In fact, one can easily see that the future values ($t = n + 1$) of L are related with the present values ($t = n$) of L by the forecasting equations:

$$\begin{cases} L(i, n + 1) = L(i, n) + 1/p_i & \text{if } L(i, n) < 1 & (8.a) \\ L(i, n + 1) = 1/p_i & \text{if } L(i, n) = 1 & (8.b) \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

with the initial condition:

$$L(i, 0) = 0 \quad (9)$$

where $i = 1, 2, \dots, I$ and I is the total number of prime planets in the PSS when time is n . Equation (8.a) tell us that we just have to add $1/p_i$ to the present fractional location in order to forecast the next fractional location of the planets.

The simple forecast rule (8.a) does not hold when a planet had finished a complete rotation and is back to its initial location, $L(i, n) = 1$. In that case the next fractional location is $1/p_i$ (Equation (8.b)).

To see in more detail how these equations work in practice, let's compute the fractional location of the six first prime planets when time $n = 17$. In this case all the information required shall be provided only by the knowledge of the Fractional Location function values when $n = 16$ (last row of Table 3).

For each planet P_i we must compare each one of values $L(i, 16)$ with p_i in order to decide which rule, (8.a) or (8.b), to apply to compute the next value of the Fractional Location, $L(i, 17)$. This computation is summarised in Table 4.

Result 1: The last known fractional locations of all planets together with Equation 8 are all one needs to compute all future locations of the prime planets.

Simplified Fractional Location function, $L_s(i, n)$.

A simplified version of Table 3 would be quit useful later on. In that simplified version (see Table 5) all cells where the values of the fractional distance are smaller than 1 are filled in with zeros:

$$\begin{cases} L_s(i, n) = 0 & \text{if } L(i, n) < 1 \\ L_s(i, n) = 1 & \text{if } L(i, n) = 1 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

After, we apply the following cleaning rule:

Cleaning rule: all zeros appearing after the last “one” in each row are replaced by an empty cell.

This simplification emphasises the time when the planets are back to their initial locations (“ones”).

3 Isomorphism between the Simplified Fractional Location function and Factorisation of Positive Integers

The fundamental theorem of arithmetic states that any positive integer can be represented in exactly one way as a product of prime numbers. Finding those prime numbers in an efficient way for a given number n , a process called factorisation, proved to be a difficult task for large values of n . However, for relatively small values of n , that factorisation can be easily achieved (see Table 6).

We are going to focus now on the last column of Table 6, more particularly on the exponents of the prime factors. We can notice that there is a clear similarity between those exponents and Table 5.

To show that similarity in all its clarity we are going to replace in that table all exponents greater than 1 by 1, and apply the cleaning rule after. The result is shown in Table 7.

The fact that Table 7 and Table 5 are identical allow us to interpret the factorisation of positive integers in terms of locations of planets in the PSS. Obviously, we can also interpret the location of the prime planets at some instant

4 Regularities in the Factorisation of Integers

The isomorphism between the output of the factorisation of integers and the location of the planets of the PSS provides a simple and visual method to find patterns and regularities in the way integers are factorised. PSS is full of periodicities and regularities and therefore it is natural that one may find them translated in the factorisation of integers.

Forecasting factors of an integer

Looking at Table 8 one can notice that the vertical distribution of “ones” is periodic for each planet. For instance, in the first column, $p_1 = 2Us$, the “ones” appear at time $m \times 2$ with $m = 1, 2, \dots$. The “zeros” appear at time $2 \times m + 1$ but with the same period as the “ones”.

Let’s now focus our attention on the first two columns of Table 8. We will notice a similar “vertical” repetition of “zeros” and “ones” highlighted by the red rectangles in Figure 3, which repeats itself every $6 (= 2 \times 3)$ rows. For instance, the pair $(1,0)$ at $n = 8$ appears as well at time $8 + m \times 6$, with $m = 1, 2, \dots$, that is $n = 14, 20, 26, 32, 38, \dots$. If we now focus on the first three columns of Table 8 we will notice a similar “vertical” repetition of “zeros” and “ones” highlighted by the blue rectangles in Figure 3 which repeats itself every $30 (= 2 \times 3 \times 5)$ time units.

For the first four columns, the repetition has a period of $210 (= 2 \times 3 \times 5 \times 7)$. In general, for the first J columns the repetition period can be written as $p_J\#$, which will be denoted by R_J .

These repetitions help in the forecast of the factors of large integers from the knowledge of the factors of smaller integers. For example, for $n = 30030$ we know that $L_s(1:5, 30030) = (1, 1, 1, 1, 1)$, that is, 30030 has 2,3,5,7 and 11 as factors. They are not the only ones since 13 is also a factor of $30030 = 2^1 \times 3^1 \times 5^1 \times 7^1 \times 11^1 \times 13^1$. Using the periodicity of the PSS with $J = 5$, that is $R_5 = 2310$, and using Result 1, we can be sure that all numbers of the form $q = 30030 + m \times 2310$ have 2, 3, 5, 7 and 11 as prime factors. For instance, for $m = 8, 453, 837$ we have $q = 19, 528, 393, 500$ which, we can now be sure of it, has 2, 3, 5, 7 and 11 as factors.

The expression $q = n + m \times R_J$ can also be written as $n = q - m \times R_J$, that is, $n = q \bmod R_J$ with $q > R_J$. For the value of q used in the previous example, the largest value of R that can be used in order to respect $q > R_J$ is $R_J = 6, 469, 693, 230$ ($J = 10$). This means that we are able to know which are, among the first 10 primes, the ones that are shared as factors by n and q , with n being given by $n = 19, 528, 393, 500 \bmod 6, 469, 693, 230$. Since $n = 119, 313, 810$, for which $L_s(1:10, n) = (1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0)$, we can conclude both, that 2, 3, 5, 7 and 11 are prime factors of q and that 13, 17, 19, 23 and 29 are not factors of q .

Result 1: If the values of $L_s(1:J, n)$ ¹ are known for some n , then, for any number of the form $q = n + m \times R_J$, it is true that $L_s(1:J, q) = L_s(1:, n)$, that is, n and q share the same J first primes as factors or not-factors. This is equivalent to say that if $n = q \bmod R_J$ is true with $q > R_J$ and $R_J = p_J\#$ then n and q share the same first J primes as factors and as not-factors.

Testing for non-primality

Following the implication expressed in Equation (12), we know that the location of the zero-starting rows in Table 8 (Figure 3) is related with prime numbers. A single zero can be find in rows located at

$$\left\{ E_{1,1} = 2 \times m + 1 \right. \quad (12)$$

that is, at the odd numbers $n = 3, 5, 7, 11, 13, \dots$.

A pair of zeros (first two columns of Table 8) can be found at, for instance, $n = 7$ and $n = 11$. Since the periodicity associated with the two first columns is $R_2 = 6$, that pair of zeros $(0,0)$ can be found at

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} E_{2,1} = 6 \times m + 1 \\ E_{2,2} = 6 \times m + 5 \end{array} \right. \quad (13)$$

¹We have introduced the colon notation “:”. “j:k” denotes a unit-spaced sequence with elements $(j, j + 1, \dots, k)$. When used as index (or argument of a function) it should be read as the span of valid values that can be used as indices or arguments. If used alone, without the limits j and k explicitly stated, it should be understood as a shorthand to state that all positive integers. Using the colon notation the expression $L_s(j, n)$ with $j = 1, \dots, J$ can be simply stated as $L_s(1 : J, n)$, that is, the range of expected values for j is stated within the brackets.

Expressions $E_{2,1:2}$ are frequently written in the form $6 \times m \pm 1$. They share a few relevant properties with $E_{1,1}$, notably:

1. If a number is a prime number then it can be written at least in one of the forms: $E_{1,1}$, $E_{2,1}$ or $E_{2,2}$
2. If a number can be written in the form $E_{1,1}$, $E_{2,1}$ or $E_{2,2}$ that number can be either a prime number or a not-prime number. For instance the number 119 can be written as $6 \times 19 - 5$ and as $2 \times 59 + 1$ and it is not-prime since it has as factors the numbers 1, 7, 17, 119.
3. If a number cannot be written in the form $E_{1,1}$, $E_{2,1}$ or $E_{2,2}$ then that number is a not-prime number. For instance, the number 24 cannot be written either as $2 \times m \pm 1$ or $6 \times m \pm 1$, therefore, we can be sure that 24 is a not-prime number.

Testing non-primality: Item 3 of the above list sets the basis for a non-primality test. Suppose the number 111. It can be written as $2 \times 55 + 1$ and $6 \times 18 + 3$. Since it cannot be written as stated by Equation (13) we can say that 111 is not-prime. In fact 111 as 1, 3, 37 and 111 as factors and, therefore, 111 is not-prime. However, 111 could be written as $2 \times m + 1$. Therefore, Equation (12) is not able to discard 111 as prime. Equation (12) is less efficient detecting not-primes than Equation (13), that is, the number of correctly detected not-primes in a large interval through Equation (13) is greater than the not-primes detected through Equation (12) for the same interval.

Generalizing

It happens that Equation (12) and (13) are the first members of a sequence of expressions, each one of them being more and more efficient detecting not-primes. The next member in that sequence of expressions is related with the triplet (0,0,0). That triplet can be found at locations 31, 37, 41, 43, 47, 49, 53 and 59 and this patterns repeats itself with a period $R_3 = 30$. We can, therefore, write that a triplet of zeros can always be found at locations $E_{3,1:8}$ given by:

$$\begin{cases} E_{3,1} = m \times 30 + 1 \\ E_{3,2} = m \times 30 + 7 \\ E_{3,3} = m \times 30 + 11 \\ E_{3,4} = m \times 30 + 13 \\ E_{3,5} = m \times 30 + 17 \\ E_{3,6} = m \times 30 + 19 \\ E_{3,7} = m \times 30 + 23 \\ E_{3,8} = m \times 30 + 29 \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

This set of expressions improves on the set E_2 , that is, for the same length of time it provides less false prime positives than the set E_2 . For instance, the set E_2 still allow multiples of five ($6 \times m + 5$) whereas no number multiple of five is produced by expressions E_3 , therefore, we can be sure that multiples of five are not prime numbers. By looking at rows starting with 4, 5, \dots , J zeros, and their periodicities, that is, $R_J = p_J \#$, one can produce sets of expressions that are more and more efficient detecting not-primes. We can write them under a general form as:

$$E_{l,b} = m \times p_l \# + s_{l,b} \quad (15)$$

where $l = 1, 2, \dots$; $m = 1, 2, \dots$ and $b = 1, 2, \dots$ and $b < 2 \times p_l$. l stands for “level”, b stands for “branch” and s stands for “seed”. The seeds in expression (14) are $s_{3,1:8} = 1, 7, 11, 13, 17, 19, 23, 29$. The seeds for the rows starting with four zeros are $s_{4,b} = 1, 11, 13, 17, 19, 23, 29, 31, 37, 41, 43, 47, 53, 59, 61, 67, 71, 73, 79, 83, 89, 97, 101, 103, 107, 109, 113, 121, 127, 131, 137, 139, 143, 149, 151, 157, 163, 167, 169, 173, 179, 181, 187, 191, 193, 197, 199, 209$. The seeds are obtained by a direct visual inspection of Table (8), Figure 3 or any other extended version or equivalent representation. The points made above can be expressed in a more general way as:

Result 2: If expressions $E_{l,b}$ cannot produce a specific integer n then that integer is not-prime. For instance, $E_{1,1}$, cannot produce even numbers then even numbers are not-prime.

Testing non-primality: If the remainder of the division of n by R_J is an element of $s_{l,b}$ then the positive integer n is not-prime.

Suppose that $n = 8\ 709\ 668\ 761\ 379\ 269\ 784\ 034\ 173\ 446\ 876\ 636\ 639\ 594\ 408\ 083\ 936\ 553\ 641\ 753\ 483\ 991\ 897\ 255\ 703\ 964\ 943\ 107\ 588\ 335\ 040\ 121\ 154\ 680\ 170\ 867\ 105\ 541\ 177\ 741\ 204\ 814\ 011\ 615\ 930\ 342\ 030\ 904\ 704\ 147\ 856\ 733\ 048\ 115\ 934\ 632\ 145\ 172\ 739\ 949\ 220\ 591\ 246\ 493\ 529\ 224\ 396\ 454\ 328\ 521\ 288\ 727\ 013$.

The division of n by $R_{100} = 8\ 709\ 668\ 761\ 379\ 269\ 784\ 034\ 173\ 446\ 876\ 636\ 639\ 594\ 408\ 083\ 936\ 553\ 641\ 753\ 483\ 991\ 897\ 255\ 703\ 964\ 943\ 107\ 588\ 335\ 040\ 121\ 154\ 680\ 170\ 867\ 105\ 541\ 177\ 741\ 204\ 814\ 011\ 615\ 930\ 342\ 030\ 904\ 704\ 147\ 856\ 733\ 048\ 115\ 934\ 632\ 145\ 172\ 739\ 949\ 220\ 591\ 246\ 493\ 529\ 224\ 396\ 454\ 328\ 521\ 288\ 726\ 490$, gives the remainder 523 . Since 523 is not an element of $s_{100,b}$ we can conclude that n is not-prime.

Location of regions with no prime numbers

Result 2 in the previous section provides a easy way to find the location of regions that are void of primes. Suppose that you would like to know where, in the sequence of integers, there is a void of length 3,000,000 . To find where one of those voids is, we will start to show how to find the location of shorter voids. An then we generalise our findings providing a expression that gives the location of the void in function of the length of the void. Note that we are not saying that we will find the location where the first void of length 3,000,000 appears in the sequence of positive integers. What is provided is the **certainty** of the location where a void of that size can be found.

Result 2 in the previous section sets the basis for our approach, that is, if expressions E cannot produce a number then that number is not-prime. By looking at $s_{3,1:8} = 1, 7, 11, 13, 17, 19, 23, 29$ and expression E_3 , we see that the numbers between 31 and 37 cannot be produced by E_3 . So, we can be sure that there should be a void of length 6 between 31 and 37. That void is a direct consequence of the void in the seed: the seed starts with 1 and then jumps to 7, this jump is then feed into E_3 producing the a void between $30 + 1$ and $30 + 7$. This mechanism applies to any level of seeds. For instance, for level 4 the seeds are $s_{4,b} = 1, 11, 13, 17, 19, 23, 29, 31, 37, 41, 43, 47, 53, 59, 61, 67, 71, 73, 79, 83, 89, 97, 101, 103, 107, 109, 113, 121, 127, 131, 137, 139, 143, 149, 151, 157, 163, 167, 169, 173, 179, 181, 187, 191, 193, 197, 199, 209$, associated with the period $R_4 = p_4\# = 210$ have a void between 1 and 11. This implies that expressions E_4 are unable to produce numbers between $p_4\# + 1$ and $p_4\# + p_4$, therefore a void of length $p_4 - 1 = 11 - 1 = 10$ is sure to exist after the number $p_4\# + 1 = 211$.

In general, $s_{l,b}$ has a void between 1 and p_l which is then translate by expressions E_l into a void of the same length $p_l - 1$ starting at $p_l\# + 1$ and ending at $p_l\# + p_l$.

Result 3: Voids of length $p_l - 1$ starting at $p_l\# + 1$ and ending at $p_l\# + p_l$ are guaranteed to exist for $l = 1, 2, \dots$.

If we now want to know where is a void of length 3,000,000 we need to calculate p_l from the expression $3000000 = p_l - 1$. This give us $l = 216816$. Therefore, after $p_{216816}\# + 1$ there is a gap of 3,000,000 without prime numbers.

Obviously $p_{216816}\#$ contains thousands of digits and is quite normal to expect to find large voids far away in the sequence of integers since the number of prime numbers by interval is known to decrease. Therefore, one could be tempted to find Result 3 evident, adding nothing new to what is already known. However, in reality, one cannot just say “look far away enough in the sequence of integers and you will find a void as large as you may want”. That strategy is not sure to achieve the goal because gaps of size 2 between 2 primes are almost sure to exist at any point of the sequence of integers, even very far away. Therefore, one is never sure where really one can find a very large void since shorter voids are among the larger ones. The power of Result 3 is that it **guarantees** a location where one can find an uninterrupted sequence of not-primes of given length.

TABLES

Table 1: Values characterising the orbits of the 6 first prime planets

Planet (P) (i^{th})	Distance (d) (Um)	Period (p) (Us)	Velocity (v) ($Um Us^{-1}$)	Angular velocity (w) ($rad Us^{-1}$)	Orbit (O) (j^{th})
1 st	2	2	2π	$2\pi/2$	2 nd
2 nd	3	3	2π	$2\pi/3$	3 rd
3 rd	5	5	2π	$2\pi/5$	5 th
4 th	7	7	2π	$2\pi/7$	7 th
5 th	11	11	2π	$2\pi/11$	11 th
6 th	13	13	2π	$2\pi/13$	13 th

Example on how to read the table using the first row:

The first planet is on the second orbit. Its distance d_1 to the sun is $2Um$.

The angular velocity with which it rotates about the sun is $w_1 = (2\pi/2) rad Us^{-1}$:

that is, it completes one rotation ($2\pi rad$) in $p_1 = 2Us$. See related Figure 1.

Table 2: Fractional Locations for the first 6 planets of PSS at time = 1 Us

Planet (P) (i^{th})	Period (p) (Us)	Angular velocity (w) ($rad Us^{-1}$)	Fractional location (L) (Dimensionless)
1 st	2	$2\pi/2$	1/2
2 nd	3	$2\pi/3$	1/3
3 rd	5	$2\pi/5$	1/5
4 th	7	$2\pi/7$	1/7
5 th	11	$2\pi/11$	1/11
6 th	13	$2\pi/13$	1/13

Table 3: Values of the Fractional Location of the six first planets of PSS from 0Us to 16Us

n	$i = 1$	$i = 2$	$i = 3$	$i = 4$	$i = 5$	$i = 6$
0	0/2	0/3	0/5	0/7	0/11	0/13
1	1/2	1/3	1/5	1/7	1/11	1/13
2	2/2	2/3	2/5	2/7	2/11	2/13
3	1/2	3/3	3/5	3/7	3/11	3/13
4	2/2	1/3	4/5	4/7	4/11	4/13
5	1/2	2/3	5/5	5/7	5/11	5/13
6	2/2	3/3	1/5	6/7	6/11	6/13
7	1/2	1/3	2/5	7/7	7/11	7/13
8	2/2	2/3	3/5	1/7	8/11	8/13
9	1/2	3/3	4/5	2/7	9/11	9/13
10	2/2	1/3	5/5	3/7	10/11	10/13
11	1/2	2/3	1/5	4/7	11/11	11/13
12	2/2	3/3	2/5	5/7	1/11	12/13
13	1/2	1/3	3/5	6/7	2/11	13/13
14	2/2	2/3	4/5	7/7	3/11	1/13
15	1/2	3/3	5/5	1/7	4/11	2/13
16	2/2	1/3	1/5	2/7	5/11	3/13

Example on how to read the table:

For the 6th Planet at time = 14Us (n=14) the value of the Fractional Distance is **1/13**.

This means that the 6th planet is at **1/13** of its orbit (as in Figure 1).

Table 4: Forecasting $L(i, 17)$ from $L(i, 16)$

Planet	$L(i, 16)$	Equation	$1/p_i$	$L(i, 17)$
1 st	2/2	(8.b) $1 = 1$	1/2	1/2
2 nd	1/3	(8.a) $1/3 < 1$	1/3	2/3 = $1/3 + 1/3$
3 rd	1/5	(8.a) $1/5 < 1$	1/5	2/5 = $1/5 + 1/5$
4 th	2/7	(8.a) $2/7 < 1$	1/7	3/7 = $2/7 + 1/7$
5 th	5/11	(8.a) $5/11 < 1$	1/11	6/11 = $5/11 + 1/11$
6 th	3/13	(8.a) $3/13 < 1$	1/13	4/13 = $3/13 + 1/13$

Table 5: Values of the Simplified Fractional Location, L_s , for time from 1Us to 16Us

Time (Us) n	Planets with periods:					
	$p_1 = 2$	$p_2 = 3$	$p_3 = 5$	$p_4 = 7$	$p_5 = 11$	$p_6 = 13$
0						
1						
2	1					
3	0	1				
4	1	0				
5	0	0	1			
6	1	1				
7	0	0	0	1		
8	1					
9	0	1				
10	1	0	1			
11	0	0	0	0	1	
12	1	1				
13	0	0	0	0	0	1
14	1	0	0	1		
15	0	1	1			
16	1					

Example on how to read the table:

At time n=15 all planets are away from their initial location with the exception of the 2nd and 3rd planet which are both back simultaneously to their initial locations.

Table 6: Extended factorisation of integers 2 to 16

Number n	Factorisation	Factors	Multiplicity	Alternative representation
2	2^1	2	1	$2^1 \cdot 3^0 \cdot 5^0 \cdot 7^0 \cdot 11^0 \cdot 13^0$
3	3^1	3	1	$2^0 \cdot 3^1 \cdot 5^0 \cdot 7^0 \cdot 11^0 \cdot 13^0$
4	2^2	2	2	$2^2 \cdot 3^0 \cdot 5^0 \cdot 7^0 \cdot 11^0 \cdot 13^0$
5	5^1	5	1	$2^0 \cdot 3^0 \cdot 5^1 \cdot 7^0 \cdot 11^0 \cdot 13^0$
6	$2^1 \cdot 3^1$	2;3	1;1	$2^1 \cdot 3^1 \cdot 5^0 \cdot 7^0 \cdot 11^0 \cdot 13^0$
7	7^1	7	1	$2^0 \cdot 3^0 \cdot 5^0 \cdot 7^1 \cdot 11^0 \cdot 13^0$
8	2^3	2	3	$2^3 \cdot 3^0 \cdot 5^0 \cdot 7^0 \cdot 11^0 \cdot 13^0$
9	3^2	3	2	$2^0 \cdot 3^2 \cdot 5^0 \cdot 7^0 \cdot 11^0 \cdot 13^0$
10	$2^1 \cdot 5^1$	2;5	1;1	$2^1 \cdot 3^0 \cdot 5^1 \cdot 7^0 \cdot 11^0 \cdot 13^0$
11	11^1	11	1	$2^0 \cdot 3^0 \cdot 5^0 \cdot 7^0 \cdot 11^1 \cdot 13^0$
12	$2^2 \cdot 3^1$	2;3	2;1	$2^2 \cdot 3^1 \cdot 5^0 \cdot 7^0 \cdot 11^0 \cdot 13^0$
13	13^1	13	1	$2^0 \cdot 3^0 \cdot 5^0 \cdot 7^0 \cdot 11^0 \cdot 13^1$
14	$2^1 \cdot 7^1$	2;7	1;1	$2^1 \cdot 3^0 \cdot 5^0 \cdot 7^1 \cdot 11^0 \cdot 13^0$
15	$3^1 \cdot 5^1$	3;5	1;1	$2^0 \cdot 3^1 \cdot 5^1 \cdot 7^0 \cdot 11^0 \cdot 13^0$
16	2^4	2	4	$2^4 \cdot 3^0 \cdot 5^0 \cdot 7^0 \cdot 11^0 \cdot 13^0$

Example on how to read the table:

For $n = 6$ the 5th row shows that $6 = 2^1 \times 3^1$, that is, 6 has 2 and 3 as multiplicative factors (whereas, for instance, 11 has just one, 11 itself).

The multiplicity (exponents) of those factors is 1 (whereas, for instance, for 8 is 3).

The last column provides a representation where factors with 0 multiplicity are kept visible as well.

Table 7: Cleaning of the “alternative representation” provided in Table 6

Integer n	Prime factors:					
	factor = 2	factor = 3	factor = 5	factor = 7	factor = 11	factor = 13
2	1					
3	0	1				
4	1	0				
5	0	0	1			
6	1	1				
7	0	0	0	1		
8	1					
9	0	1				
10	1	0	1			
11	0	0	0	0	1	
12	1	1				
13	0	0	0	0	0	1
14	1	0	0	1		
15	0	1	1			
16	1					

Example on how to read the table:

Number 8 has a single factor: 2. Multiplicity is ignored.

Table 8: Factorising the integers 17, 18, 19, 20, and 21 using Equation 8

Integer n	Prime factors:					
	factor = 2	factor = 3	factor = 5	factor = 7	factor = 11	factor = 13
2	1					
3	0	1				
4	1					
5	0	0	1			
6	1	1				
7	0	0	0	1		
8	1					
9	0	1				
10	1	0	1			
11	0	0	0	0	1	
12	1	1				
13	0	0	0	0	0	1
14	1	0	0	1		
15	0	1	1			
16	1					
17	0	0	0	0	0	0
18	1	1				
19	0	0	0	0	0	0
20	1	0	1			
21	0	1	0	1		

Equations 8 are not enough to correctly factorise 17 and 19.

This is solved by Equation 11.

APPENDIX

Forecasting new prime numbers

In order to see how the Equations 8, 10 and 11 allow the forecast of new primes and the factorisation of all integers, let's start by the initial situation at time $n = 0$ when a single prime planet is known ($I = 1$) and its period is 2, that is:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} n = 0 \\ i = 1 \\ I = 1 \\ J = \text{not defined} \\ p_1 = 2 \\ L(1,0) = 0 \end{array} \right. \quad (16)$$

With these initial conditions the forecast equations provide the following results for time $n + 1$:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} L(1,0+1) = L(1,0) + 1/p_1 & \text{applicable since } L(1,0) < 1 \\ L(1,0+1) = 1/p_1 & \text{not applicable since } L(1,0) \text{ does not respect the condition } L(1,0) = 1 \end{array} \right. \quad (17)$$

Hence, $L(1,1) = 0 + 1/2 = 1/2$. Equation 11 is not used since J is not defined. Therefore, we have a new set of initial conditions:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} n = 1 \\ i = 1 \\ I = 1 \\ J = \text{not defined} \\ p_1 = 2 \\ L(1,1) = 1/2 \end{array} \right. \quad (18)$$

which can be fed again into Equation 8 to forecast the new values of L at time $n = 2$:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} L(1,1+1) = (L(1,1) + 1)/p_1 & \text{applicable since } L(1,1) < 1 \\ L(1,1+1) = 1/p_1 & \text{not applicable since } L(1,1) \text{ does not respect the condition } L(1,1) = 1 \end{array} \right. \quad (19)$$

Hence, $L(1,2) = 1/2 + 1/2 = 1$. Again, Equation 11 is not used since the condition $n - 2 \geq 1$ for $n = 2$ is not verified. The new set of initial conditions is:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} n = 2 \\ i = 1 \\ I = 1 \\ J = \text{not defined} \\ p_1 = 2 \\ L(1,2) = 1 \end{array} \right. \quad (20)$$

which can be fed again into Equation 11 to forecast the new values of L at time $n = 3$:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} L(1,2+1) = L(1,2) + 1/p_1 & \text{not applicable since } L(1,2) \text{ does not respect the condition } L(1,2) < 1 \\ L(1,2+1) = 1/p_1 & \text{applicable since } L(1,2) = 1 \end{array} \right. \quad (21)$$

Hence, $L(1,3) = 1/2$. In this case, Equation 11 can be used since the condition $n - 2 \geq 1$ for $n = 3$ is verified. We need nevertheless to know the values of J and of L_s in order to compute the summation in Equation 11. J is the number of prime planets in the system at time $n = 3$, that is, $J = I = 1$, and since $L_s(1,3) = 0$, Equation 11 tells us that 3 is a prime number. This is the same to say that there is a new planet in the Prime Solar System ($I = 2$)

with a period $p_2 = 3$. The new set of initial conditions is then:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Independent of the planet:} \\ n = 3, I = 2, J = 1 \\ \text{Depending on the planet:} \\ i = 1, \quad \quad \quad i = 2 \\ p_1 = 2, \quad \quad \quad p_2 = 3 \\ L(1, 3) = 1/2, \quad \quad L(2, 3) = 0 \end{array} \right. \quad (22)$$

which can be fed again into Equation 11 to forecast the new values of L at time $n = 4$:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} L(1, 3 + 1) = L(1, 3) + 1/p_1 & \text{applicable since } L(1, 3) < 1 \\ L(1, 3 + 1) = 1/p_1 & \text{not applicable since } L(1, 3) \neq 1 \\ L(2, 3 + 1) = L(2, 3) + 1/p_2 & \text{applicable since } L(2, 3) < 1 \\ L(2, 3 + 1) = 1/p_2 & \text{not applicable since } L(2, 3) \neq 1 \end{array} \right. \quad (23)$$

Hence, $L(1, 4) = 1$, $L(2, 4) = 1/3$. Equation 11 can be used with $J = 1$ but since the sum gives the value $1 \neq 0$ we can conclude that $n = 4$ is not a prime number and no new prime planet should be added to the Prime Solar system. The new set of initial conditions is then (note that J for $n = 4$ is 2) :

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Independent of the planet:} \\ n = 3, I = 2, J = 2 \\ \text{Depending on the planet:} \\ i = 1, \quad \quad \quad i = 2 \\ p_1 = 2, \quad \quad \quad p_2 = 3 \\ L(1, 4) = 1, \quad \quad \quad L(2, 4) = 1/3 \end{array} \right. \quad (24)$$

which can be fed again into Equation 11 to forecast the new values of L at time $n = 5$:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} L(1, 5) = L(1, 4) + 1/p_1 & \text{not applicable since } L(1, 4) < 1 \text{ is not true} \\ L(1, 5) = 1/p_1 & \text{applicable since } L(1, 4) = 1 \\ L(2, 5) = L(2, 4) + 1/p_2 & \text{applicable since } L(2, 3) < 1 \\ L(2, 5) = 1/p_2 & \text{not applicable since } L(2, 3) \neq 1 \end{array} \right. \quad (25)$$

Hence, $L(1, 5) = 1/2$, $L(2, 5) = 2/3$. Equation 11 can be used with $J = 2$. Since $L_s(1, 5) = 0$, $L_s(2, 5) = 0$ by Equation 10, the sum in Equation 11 gives the value 0 and therefore we can conclude that $n = 5$ is a prime number and a new prime planet should be added to the Prime Solar system. This is similar to the situation we have already worked for $n = 3$. By continuing to feed Equation 8, 10 and 11 and taking care to update J at the right time, one can forecast all prime numbers.